

CRIMINALISTIC AND CRIMINOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE THOMAS RESTOBAR CASE IN PERU IN THE CONTEXT OF SANITARY MEASURES BY COVID 19: CASE STUDY

Abstract.

A qualitative approach study was developed, with a case study design, the primary sources of information used came from seven professional experts. The focus group technique was used to collect the information, applying a script validated by five experts. It was evidenced that the deficiencies in the six structured subcategories should have influenced the death of thirteen people by asphyxiation; the people who attended the place did not comply with the sanitary norms, exposing the health and life of their relatives and other people; the actors of the place and of the Municipality of Los Olivos, did not comply with the execution of the norms of supervision and control; finally generating a meta-category "The categorization and socialization of the experience", which would allow other cases not to be repeated.

Keywords. Criminology; Legislation; criminal law; Social and economic law.

Annex 01. Instruments

Semi-structured questionnaire for interviewing professional justice operators

Regarding the study of the THOMAS RESTOBAR case IN PERU WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF THE DECLARATION OF SANITARY MEASURES; The questionnaire was applied to him so that he needs his experience and professional studies, what was his perception of the intervention of the different actors responsible for the criminal investigation.

Focus Group guide for professional justice operators.

1. How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?
2. What are the advantages and disadvantages of the double participation of the national police and the Public Ministry, in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports, which will determine the formalization of the fiscal accusation?
3. Do you know if the criminalistic work of the Prosecutor, expert witnesses and investigations have the action protocols for their work and if these are found in the transparency portals of instruction?
4. What is your opinion regarding the case of Thomas Restobar and the actions of the institutions involved in opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of the police, criminal and Public Ministry protocols?
5. What is your opinion of the Thomas Restobar case and of the action of the Municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks Lima Norte-Diris and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health?
6. From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

Annex 02. Informed consent used for focus group participants

Informed consent to participate in a law and health research project

You are being invited to participate in this law and health research study. Before deciding whether or not to participate, you should know and understand each of the following sections.

Project title: CRIMINALISTIC AND CRIMINOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE THOMAS RESTOBAR CASE IN PERU WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF THE DECLARATION OF SANITARY MEASURES BY COVID 19: CASE STUDY

Name of the principal investigators: Dr. José Antonio Jáuregui Montero; Dr. Oriana Rivera Lozada; Dr. Carlos Neyra Rivera; Dr. César Antonio Bonilla Asalde.

Purpose of the study: Collect and interpret the experiences on the application of criminal and criminological protocols and procedures, which were used when carrying out the investigation of the Thomas Restobar case in Peru within the context of the declaration of sanitary measures by Covid 19.

Benefits for participating: You have the possibility of knowing the results of the research by the most appropriate means (individually or in groups) that can be very useful in your professional activity.

Disadvantages and risks: None, you will only be asked to answer the questionnaire.

Cost to Participate: You will not incur any costs during the study.

Confidentiality: The information you provide will be protected, only the researchers can know. Other than this confidential information, you will not be identified when the results are published.

Resignation: You may withdraw from the study at any time, without penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled.

Subsequent consultations: If you have additional questions during the development of this study or about the research, you can contact Patricia Ochoa Vega, team coordinator.

Contact with the Ethics Committee: If you have questions about your rights as a volunteer, or if you think that your rights have been violated, you can contact the president of the Ethics Committee of the Norbert Wiener University, located in block 4, Av. Arequipa - Lime.

Voluntary Participation: Your participation in this study is completely voluntary and you may withdraw at any time.

DECLARATION OF CONSENT I declare that I have read and understood, had time and opportunity to ask questions, which were answered satisfactorily, I have not been coerced or unduly influenced to participate or continue to participate in the study and that I finally agree to participate voluntarily in the study .

Signature of research participant

ID

Annex 03. Transcript of the participations

The primary information sources used come from seven Peruvian professional experts who are students of the master's degree in Criminal Sciences at a Peruvian University, selected incidentally: a police crime scene expert (E1), a biologist (E2), a psychologist from the Ministry of Women (E3), a Social Specialist lawyer from the Ministry of Women and Vulnerable Populations (E4), 2 prosecutors from the Public Ministry (E5, E6), a lawyer from the Superior Court of Specialized Criminal Justice (E7).

For the collection of information, the focus group technique was used, for which a script validated by five experts in law was designed, for this purpose six open questions were applied, in such a way that the experts can express themselves without limitations in their answers. For the development of the focus group, the health provisions in force by Covid 19 were taken into consideration, taking place virtually on the Microsoft Teams platform, being recorded in audio and video, after which they were transcribed and evaluated.

Therefore, the transcripts ordered by experts are presented:

Interventions and answers of (E1)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the studies of the criminalistic procedures?

We have seen that the first level of protection that should have been carried out by the police officers who intervened, they themselves have violated this protocol, they have not protected the crime scene as it should have been, because they took the DVR, the content of the images Of video; From that point on, the crime scene was already altered and the quality and criminal procedures were affected by this violation, it is assumed that the police intervention already took place, the event occurred, they should only have protected the scene and no longer subtract no place. Because those objects or those elements would become test items; example in this case the video images are a material element, it is a document and has been taken from the place.

The second level already consists of the approach of the criminology experts; This level was also violated, the evidence elements were modified and destroyed because, when the experts made their inspection, they did not find the DVR, the database of the video images, they would have been stolen from the place, I consider an important point that violation to this team of utmost importance.

Regarding quality, who supervises quality, is there someone who says at the end the work is well done or bad, is it regular or is it very good?

Someone who supervises, well in this case the only one who would give a certain control of legality or that a due procedure has been followed in relation to the approach of the experts, in a certain way has been the representative of the Public Ministry, but a quality in relation to the results, I think there has been no quality of the results. Wouldn't you know how to explain it? What would this be...? How could the quality of the results of the procedures be guaranteed?

Oh now, it does refer to a type of quality such as ISO, not really, there is no ISO, we don't even have laboratories with a quality ISO.

Well no, there is not, there is no quality of the laboratory in relation to criminalistics, I don't know, if both the police and the public ministry have an ISO, at least in the police I think not, it does not exist.

From your point of view, what role does the press play? ... fulfills a political role of control? How does it help the staff to work better or on the contrary does it suddenly hinder the work?

It can be for or it can be against. In favor it would be, when before arriving at the scene of the crime they find out the facts as they have been, and against when they arrive after the events, the press enters the facts and begins to film what they can find or what they find, things that, in the second level of approach, the experts have overlooked that element; for example, when the boarding level was given, the press was first inspected; ... there were two moments of inspection, according to the media; when there were some victims in the place, the first inspection was carried out, in this first inspection the press had not yet become aware that the DVR was missing, that is, the press became aware when an expanded inspection was carried out, there the press only realized that the DVR was missing; the Public Ministry assumed that investigation; whether they were or would have been intentionally deleted, deleted, or deleted by the system itself.

Question 2: What are the advantages and disadvantages of a dual participation of the National Police and the Public Ministry in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports that will determine the fiscal classification?

That is to say, the fact that there are experts from the national police and also from the public prosecutor's office, that double criminal function, where the logistics, the personnel, are distributed; is beneficial or harmful. What assessment would you have against that?

I believe that it is an advantage to have two institutions that deal with the criminalistic aspect, because the police do not comply with certain standards, the Public Ministry does not have the number of personnel to deal with a crime scene, I understand that some samples that The investigations are collected, it is the prosecutor who decides where to send this sample, I think that while more institutions are dedicated to processing samples for an optimal successful result, there should be more institutions that provide this quality. Not even one other institution complements itself, it always needs help from other institutions, both logistical and personal.

At present, because in our reality both institutions see the issue of criminalistics, if we are going to talk about the laws, the one who is leading the direction of the criminal investigation are the representatives of the MP, they decide if they think it is convenient they can decide to which laboratory to send that sample, so that it can be processed either to the MP or PNP laboratory.

Well, I think that, if there is a private company that has adequate ISO laboratory quality, I think it would be feasible to use a private company, because, as I told you before, neither the National Police laboratory nor the Public Ministry have quality certification. ISO and quality standards, so it could be questioned; I wouldn't know how to tell you that all of a sudden your equipment is no longer in use and you don't have the necessary logistics.

Question 3: Do you know if the criminalistic work of the prosecutor, official experts, party and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these protocols are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

No, in itself I have not seen, ... what the protocols are provided in the portals of the institutions. It should be in the public domain, so a lawyer from either the defense or the prosecution can have access to this information.

Question 4: What is your opinion regarding the Thomas Restobar case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody of the police, criminalistic and prosecutorial protocols?

In relation to Opportunity, it is also according to the place where the event took place, both the national police and the public ministry, suddenly one of the two arrives first, the other later, suddenly there is a lack of more fluid communication between both institutions .

I believe that it has been a media case, I do believe that they have arrived in a timely manner because it has been seen in the press that both institutions have worked together, both the Public Ministry, as well as personnel of police criminalistics experts.

They did not act well from there the chain of custody was already altered, contaminated.

From the first level, the chain of custody was already being violated, it is assumed that the first responders should have protected this scene and they are the Guardians of this evidence; if from there the chain of custody has already been violated, ... protecting, isolating the scene of the crime or the place of the event is already creating a chain of custody.

I consider that neither the MP nor the Experts were aware of this violation, until they arrived at the place where this DVR was missing and they were able to notice it. Well, this DVR was no longer there, and they didn't know if it had been the people who were in the place or if it had been the police. There was a question: who would have stolen this DVR?

When both institutions arrived at the scene of the crime... they already found a protected scene, but when they began to carry out their inspection they verified that, at some point, the protection was violated and that is where this question arises. What happened to this DVR? Was there or was there not this DVR? If there had been, had they been signed or had they not been signed when the events occurred? facts. So I consider that it has not acted properly.

And regarding the tear gas canisters, if the experts were able to collect some elements that were the subject of evidence or if they were able to determine whether these devices were used or not?

Well, in the press it was implied that, due to the comments of these participants in this event, they stated that the police had... used tear gas, but... I imagine, well, if they had this hypothesis, this information must have exhausted the means of searching. to obtain these chemical substances, because the chemical elements contained in these tear gas can be impregnated in clothing as well as in the walls and ceiling of this place, and now if they have followed the chain of custody protocols, I imagine that the prosecutor should be aware that these forms are drawn up at the scene, to ensure that this sample is authentic until it is processed in the crime lab.

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

I think that in the preventive part there should have been, ... they have responsibility, if we are in a state of emergency, the one in charge of ensuring it is fulfilled is the municipality, because that place should have been closed, why was it open at that time? suddenly there was no serenazgo

What's more, it was also said that they had been working for a long time, so the preventive part of the municipality has been failing.

Did they do the required necropsy in the morgue regarding the cause of death?

I understand that most of these young people who died, most of the young people who underwent surgery had COVID, most of them had COVID, I don't know how many there were, I don't remember exactly 20, I think they had COVID

Do you know if they did an autopsy on those corpses or who collected the corpses?

Well, in this case, it will have been the police by fiscal disposition so that they are admitted to the morgue.

Was that disposition correct or should it have been DIGESA who should have been wearing appropriate clothing?

I believe that DIGESA should have intervened first

So it may have been a bad fiscal disposition?

Of course, suddenly there was a bad fiscal disposition, because as you refer to an act of flagrante delicto where the police found these young people in the premises dancing as a result of this intervention; Well, I consider it a bad intervention because there were deaths.

Of course, then if the National Police knew that an event was taking place in this place, they should have coordinated with DIGESA.

So the DIGESA protocols were not used to remove the corpses and avoid contamination.

They assumed that they were dead by suffocation or crushing, but they did not rule out whether they had COVID or not, therefore, the handling of these bodies also generated contagion for both the intervening personnel and the prosecutor, they could have been infected

Do you know if they did the necropsy or not?

No, I have no knowledge of whether or not they did an autopsy.

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

To improve criminalistic work, for example, the training of experts. Is there currently a forensic planimetric expert, from the National Police or the Public Ministry?

A specialist in forensic planimetry, No, there is not

Do you know of any course, have you ever heard of a course that Dynamic Retrospective has been taught in Peru, are there institutions that train this type of professional?

Well, in reality, expert psychologists are not committed to carrying out these psychological tests as psychological necropsies, it would be for them a kind of psychobiological assessment

Is there any kind of training for the forensic photographer?

The forensic photographer itself does not exist, the courses given by the police or the Public Ministry only give a profile of a crime scene expert, but in other countries the crime scene expert is the one who directs, organizes and plans and the forensic photographer is Part of your team of course. I know that in the Directorate of Criminalistics there is an area of forensic photography.

There is a shortcoming because the forensic photographer with the photographic views is documenting how the crime scene is for an upcoming reconstruction, therefore, adequate preparation is needed to apply forensic photography.

I believe that there should be protocols for everyone, for cases of homicides, robberies, well established that are public domain.

Interventions and answers of (E2)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?

One element that has to do with the quality of the procedures is related to the training that the personnel may have and the other is the implementation of the departments of the units in charge of applying our procedures; In another course, from the master's degree, I also commented on the report of the ombudsman, which mentioned the deficiencies, that the criminalistics department had, they did not have the investigation kit, the equipment, the mobile units and all this affects the investigations , then this is in accordance with what was stated in the yes question, How

are we prepared, guarantee quality It seems to me that if we do not abide by the report, we are still lacking; let's say what if we can gather through experience, from the specialists of the experts,

I am not aware, if there is an area that sees this quality, this unit should be very technical, very specialized, that is independent of political issues or any other distorting influence, rather it can be used for other purposes. It does seem opportune and necessary to me that there be a unit to verify the procedures and really contribute to improving the work of the investigators.

I don't know if there is an area that looks at quality; it should be very specialized outside of political interests or influences, because it could be used for other purposes. It seems to me that it is timely and necessary that there be a unit to verify the procedures

Question 2: What are the advantages and disadvantages of the dual participation of the National Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports?

Regarding the advantage and disadvantage of the double participation of both the National Police and the Public Ministry, I think that the advantage is that both can contribute to a criminal investigation, especially when one of them is better positioned and has better resources, to carry out an expert opinion, this helps that these two instances can participate and can intervene in an investigation.

The disadvantages that could occur are I think, at the time of the issuance of skills; if it is that the 2 participate and they are two experts of the same specialty where a contradiction could arise, but if we are already talking about the formalization of the complaint, it could not be done because the prosecutor is not going to present two expert opinions; what yes probably the fact that there are these criminalistic procedures both in the police and the Public Ministry can ensure and contribute to the fiscal work, this instance that we have commented previously would have to intervene what is INACAL to ensure that these procedures are correct and above all to that there is uniformity, between these two entities that are the National Police and the Public Ministry and this, above all, avoid a disparity in terms of the capacity to carry out the investigation,

Truly, I am just seeing this idea of unifying, this perspective of unifying, it seems to me that these units, these departments of both entities, could rather be integrated and form part of a single criminal investigation entity, but I do not agree that this private but that it is also a public instance, I think that our case above all because of the dynamics of our country, I think that it would contribute because now there is currently a disparity because one of them has better

equipment and another may be in deficit, and it also depends on how manages the assigned budget internally. I believe that an integrated specialized criminalistics unit would help not only the investigation, but the procedures could also be unique and would allow greater control and advantage in compliance.

Question 3: Do you know if the criminalistic work of the prosecutor, official experts, party experts and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

I see that, if there are these action protocols to intervene in these investigations, but they are not easily accessible; when I try to identify the web pages and I can't locate them easily and in the places where I find them they are not all, let's say in the MP, I have been able to locate more of the forensic medicine ones, but as a proposal like you it is finally pointed out what could be done to complying with this standard of transparency there should probably be a portal or something, some virtual mechanism that is specifically to disseminate and publicize all these procedures that are generally given in all institutions, very important to be carried out on a single web page or other computer device , but in any case it should be centralized and that would help all of us who are involved in this issue.

Question 4: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of police, criminal and prosecutorial protocols?

According to the information that has been obtained, it is still prowling, it seems that the procedures have not been complied with, first what has to do with the intervention and then the analysis of the cameras that were later broadcast, allowed us to see the contradictions that had been given in the first versions of the case, and this has led to the determination that, above all, the police protocols have not been complied with, including the participation of the municipality, which in this case also had an oversight and control task. this type of business and that this would not have been fulfilled either.

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

Regarding the action of the Municipality of Los Olivos, I believe that it has these two tasks of prevention and the responsibility of the criminal aspect, I believe that if it had to have fulfilled its task of control and supervision of these businesses, it seems that it had previously been denied a license, that is, this place already had problems, it was already a place that needed more attention; It is estimated that there were more than 100 people, so it was time to provide and one could alert that if 50, 60, 70 people are entering a site, it could have already been intervened before, that all the concentration and all the activity of this orchestra has already begun that was also there, that is, there were elements that one could already work with beforehand, knowing the background of this place. As for the Ministry of Health, I think so,

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

Regarding how criminalistic work should be improved and how it should contribute to training, I think that one issue that should be worked on is training through a simulated scene, in this way knowing how a crime scene is altered and how it can obstruct the work of the investigation, will help the work of the investigators above all to be able to systematize these actions carried out by criminal elements and thereby prevent the results of an investigation from being distracted or taken elsewhere, also this issue of criminal profiles allows us to determine the patterns which are the constants that these people perform specifically in the aspect of the simulation of a crime scene. Regarding the disciplines or professions that could be strengthened, it seems to me that it would be important for forensic psychology, I believe that this discipline would contribute a lot, to know all the internal dynamics and how it is produced characterizing these criminal minds and this would help us not only to level of investigation but also at the level of prevention, I believe that a challenge for forensic psychology is to standardize procedures at the level of all the instances where these professionals work, we are talking about the sectors of the executive power, the judiciary, the Public Ministry or the local governments could have the same instruments or methodologies for the evaluation I think that would be a bit of a pending task, which is in this discipline and, I think that once this is achieved we must consolidate, This is going to be a great contribution to criminal investigation.

I would like to emphasize at this time that I comment that many deficiencies and weaknesses can be found within this criminal investigation procedure. I think it is also important

to recognize that the experts, despite these difficulties, despite these limitations, have a lot to do with with the budget, implementations and that these specialists simply have not given up their function and with the tools they had, with the resources they had, and with the training they have received, they have been responding and contributing to the investigation criminal and I would like the experience of these experts to be collected in the commissions that are going to be formed, because really according to my experience I have seen how from the outside you can identify some aspects that they ignore or do not take into account, and something that is missing is the systematization of their experience, this is something that has to be reinforced, many of these people have years doing specialized investigations, in a certain area but they have not been able to organize, systematize, on the other hand, we see that people who have not had all this experience that these professionals of the public mystery police have, then they are specialists, lecturers, exhibitors or they even publish books, when they have not had the full journey and all the extensive work that an expert has in these institutions, then, in my proposal is that in this commission these opinions can be taken into account, which I do not know is obvious, that it is not assumed from the outside that it is what it should be, professionals should be listened to, experts who have been working for many years and that in any case, if there is something that should also be influenced in training, it is being able to help how to systematize all this experience.

Interventions and answers of the (E3)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?

Yes, doctor, regarding the first question, there is documentation that the police should have carried out at the time of one of the experts. At the time of carrying out their work, we have legislative decrees that strengthen the police criminalistic function, for example, legislative decree 1219 of September 23, 2015 ; there is a manual for the development of the investigation plan there is a criminalistics manual of the National Police of Peru number 1299-05 DIRGEN, of July 2, 2005, manuals of expert criminalistics procedures there is a manual of operational investigation procedures, then all these guidelines that you have, to be able to carry out quality criminal proceedings and results, because sometimes people think that they already have the necessary experience, they do it in a simple way, without being thorough because in criminalistics what is required is to be thorough at a crime scene, so many times a comparison and evaluation of how they are investigated is not done correctly, so the quality of the result will vary, It requires to be

an expert to have enough experience of the matter. So in this case Thomás apparently it has not been carried out correctly, it has been wanted as in any investigation that is carried out, but it has not had an effective result.

In general, despite the fact that there are quite a few manuals, decrees, criminal proceedings, it is only being carried out, in a general way, on a daily basis, according to custom, it is not carried out as indicated in the manuals, but what they want is to have a result, for not taking the quality of that result of the criminal proceedings in the right way is not going to be totally true.

So, in conclusion, we are not prepared to guarantee quality, even though there is information, even though there are procedures, they are not carried out, that is why the results are always delayed or sometimes they are not true.

Apparently I have not been aware that there is an area that supervises the fulfillment of the tasks regarding criminalistics, at least in the news, documents do not exist, I am not aware that this area exists.

Question 2: What are the advantages and disadvantages of dual participation, the National Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office, in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports?

How it is known to all of us, but there are two institutions that perform the same criminalistic function, both the National Police and the Public Ministry are empowered, both carry out these procedures.

It is known that the Public Ministry does not have enough personnel in the area of criminalistics for cases at the national level, so that is why police criminalistics personnel are required, who have training to develop both in criminalistic procedures and in the issuance of reports, but rigorous training should be carried out in the case of the police because their initial academic studies - when they are preparing are not specific to being an expert - but after they have finished they already do it when they finish their degree in police; they decide which field to follow and that is where some decide to belong to the area of criminology they receive training but their training should be more constant, there was an opportunity doctor where, I wanted, I was in a police area here in Lima and I saw that sign that said; training for experts for some branch in particular and it turned out that they told me that I couldn't because I had to have the requirements of being a police officer, so these trainings are voluntary but it should be, well, in that case

mandatory for each branch, on the other hand the advantage of the participation of the Public Ministry can be; We see that in the area of the public ministry to enter the Public Ministry they ask for certain requirements to be an expert, they also have a ballot, what requirements should they have, studies, experience; I believe that to be an expert, you should not have enough experience and the advantage of the participation of both institutions means that all criminal investigations can be carried out at the national level, However, the disadvantage is regarding the training and quality of results in the procedures of the expert reports, as I had mentioned in the case of the police, the personnel of the Public Prosecutor's Office do not have enough or are lacking, in some areas it is impossible for them to arrive, as well as by the number of cases to be investigated; but if the State would provide compulsory training with these courses, whether they are national or international, I believe that the criminalistics area of the national police could improve, and with respect to the Public Ministry as an entity of the State, it should also train, it is good that they have entered with a certain profile but they should continue training because every year crime advances according to technology, which is a quite considerable contribution for criminals.

It seems to me that if the police unites with the Public Ministry; they have different salary incomes, if both would be in the same area they would have the same benefits, I imagine, anyway the State invests in its areas of the MP and PNP, either with materials and the same work itself, then if we are going to to have a company manage it, I think that in my opinion it would be good, because it is private and public at the same time; Because it is private, I believe that it will be done correctly and strictly in order to have good results. However, it will not be changing, but rather it will be more rigid. Here it will be constantly evaluated and trained, because in the end, after; for example in the judiciary - in my institution - it is the case of the interpreters - they are a private company - where the judiciary hires them, So in this case it would be the same. So in my opinion if we unify; There are no longer going to be problems, that the police do not comply with the documents, or are delayed, because one of the answers given by the police is that they have a lot of work to do and that it takes time because they are attending to other sectors, however, if becomes private, there will be an area specialized in delivering these documents, it will be delivered on time, and thus all investigations, expert reports, among others, will be carried out more effectively.

Question 3: Do you know if the criminalistic work of the prosecutor, official experts, party experts and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

As far as I know, the action protocols for their work should be found, if there are criminal protocols, but I have not observed that they are found in the institutional transparency portals, I think they should make this part more noticeable, but to date I have not observed this.

Question 4: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of police, criminal and prosecutorial protocols?

The actions that had been carried out, from the first moment, in my opinion, were not correct, a chain of custody was not established as it should have been because at that moment people began to approach, the relatives, suddenly they have moved some or another object, on the other hand, in the case of the police cameras, a version was given first, then they changed it, when they just saw the restobar cameras they realized that it was not what the police had mentioned from the beginning on television, that is there has been an accumulation of lies for not wanting to be involved in this case, although it is true that they were not complying with the rules established in a state of emergency of not holding any type of social gatherings, and also taking into account the time in which had taken this and also despite the fact that within that place there were people who had requisitions, in spite of all this they had to act with corresponding police protocols, they did not organize themselves correctly with respect to the subject of criminalistics, they did not have a specific chain of custody, even the next day, people kept coming, even though they broke down the door, but there were people who were close to the area, the police should have taken greater care to keep the population away at that time, well, if they had taken carried out a good application of everything that we had mentioned throughout this conversation, I believe that there would not have been these types of impasses, that despite the fact that the police intervened in the end there were several deaths and all this is related to the case of Utopia, there was no compliance with the use of protocols, they acted on impulse and did not measure the consequences of their police intervention.

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

I think that Thomas had already had problems with the municipality of Los Olivos, at this point I think that he should have warned, he should have carried out inspections of the premises because it is a local in his area, they must carry out constant inspections, what is that based on, in that it did not have good signage, it did not have the conditions for a restobar, for example it had only one entrance and exit staircase, it was not carried out, because I believe that if an inspection had been carried out previously, or it would have been a corresponding fine to fix that aspect if in case they wanted it to be an environment that continues with its work, I think it would have avoided so many victims, when the police entered.

After this unfortunate event, the municipality of Los Olivos appeared, announcing the events it had had with this restobar.

On the other hand, the directorate of integrated health networks in Lima Norte did not, in fact, the entire Ministry of Health collaborated regarding the COVID 19 tests, the rapid tests for both the police and the detainees, unfortunately almost the majority came out positive in the test COVID, Regarding the positives, they were told that they should quarantine, but that is not known, we must take into account that our population, despite the fact that they are infected with COVID, not everyone has the will to quarantine and not infect others, so for this reason, and also the Ministry of Health says that surveillance is carried out on people who have COVID, but it is not done constantly, even for Peru a test is difficult and that arrive quickly, then on that side the Ministry of Health, At least with the experiences that I have observed, they are not aware of the people who have COVID, so this topic, I believe that of a person who has COVID, or of a group of people who began to spread it, it was an absolute contagion on the day of the events, because they were with a minimum distance, and that is how the police officers were infected, so in my opinion the Municipality should have warned of these events beforehand, because after that, there is not much that it can contribute, for future changes, are carried out when everything returns to normal, they should be more rigorous with the issue of seeing the locations, zones, inspections of the premises to avoid some type of event like the present. I believe that from a person who has COVID, or from a group of people who began to spread it, it was an absolute contagion on the day of the events, because they were with a minimum distance, and that is how the police officers became infected, so to me It seems that the Municipality should have warned of these events beforehand, because after that, there is not much that it can contribute, for future changes, they are made when everything returns to normal, they should be more rigorous with the issue of seeing

the locations, areas , inspections to the premises to avoid some type of facts like the present one.I believe that from a person who has COVID, or from a group of people who began to spread it, it was an absolute contagion on the day of the events, because they were with a minimum distance, and that is how the police officers became infected, so to me It seems that the Municipality should have warned of these events beforehand, because after that, there is not much that it can contribute, for future changes, they are made when everything returns to normal, they should be more rigorous with the issue of seeing the locations, areas , inspections to the premises to avoid some type of facts like the present one.So, in my opinion, the Municipality should have warned of these events beforehand, because after that, there is not much that it can contribute, for future changes, made when everything returns to normal, they should be more rigorous with the issue of seeing the locations, areas, inspections of premises to avoid some type of event like this.So, in my opinion, the Municipality should have warned of these events beforehand, because after that, there is not much that it can contribute, for future changes, made when everything returns to normal, they should be more rigorous with the issue of seeing the locations, areas, inspections of premises to avoid some type of event like this.

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

Then we have a general analysis to close this meeting from your perception what change you think should be implemented to improve right now for example fossil formation

No, but nevertheless within everything I also have some criminal specialties of forensic sciences that have not yet been developed or are very incipient in our reality, so the question is what do you think should be implemented, should some other forensic sciences be implemented, or only, well, all of a sudden improve what we have.

Yes, I think that it would start from a good training, I think that the studies are a great tool that can be had for the development of criminalistics in this case, for example, some type of reforms should also be made to the reports, with From experience, I have observed that there are reports that sometimes have a structure that could even be improved, the part of the conclusions that of some of the reports should be more explanatory because they said that from time to time the stage of an oral trial arrives the reports as in the judicial file and there these reports have to

detail the magistrates so that they can have certainty at the moment of being able to decide content to have information of each one, but in a clear and concise way, sometimes that is very vague in the answers of the conclusions or very technical, in which we need the presence of those experts, sometimes this issue is not problematic, because there should be something specific in the standard in the case of the inconsistencies of the experts, although it is true when an expert does not attend the call of a magistrate or collegiate, a warning can be requested, but because we are extending these issues so much, if it were the case that those reports were clear and precise, and they would not cause any type of doubt, their presence would not even be necessary, but when we request their presence, it turns out that they do not even answer us, we are calling repeatedly, in the case of the police they are sent documents, but I have had more problems with the experts from the Prosecutor's Office, that when they are notified for a certain case, with respect to a specific case not all of them usually come, when they are informed, their institution tells us that the expert has not yet, already has notified but it is not known if he will attend or not, so I think that to be an expert you need a lot of commitment, because all his cases that an expert report is being carried out are of greater burden, they are not so important for a clarification of an oral trial, which is already the culminating stage of a process, and sometimes even a doctor with the subject of expert reports does not, there have been inconveniences that have made even the parties doubt, for which it has required experts on the part, to that a confrontation can be carried out between the report the first expert no, and the one from the police and that from the police or from a member of the Public Ministry with the report, that also means that a lot of time is wasted for a process, I think there should be more commitment, more study, we have to bear in mind, doctor, that every year new investigations suddenly appear, new procedures because they are based a lot on old techniques and for a good expert report you need not the latest technologies, mechanisms have already improved and I don't know if they change the mechanisms and change some aspects of the investigation, then the structure of the reports should also change. I think there should be more commitment to further study, we have to bear in mind, doctor, that every year new investigations suddenly appear, new procedures because they are largely based on old techniques, and for a good expert report, we need the latest technologies, not the latest mechanisms. They have already improved and I don't know if the mechanisms change and some aspects of the investigation change, so the structure of the reports should also change. I think there should be more commitment to further study, we have to bear in mind, doctor, that every year new investigations suddenly appear, new procedures

because they are largely based on old techniques, and for a good expert report, we need the latest technologies, not the latest mechanisms. They have already improved and I don't know if the mechanisms change and some aspects of the investigation change, so the structure of the reports should also change. We have to take into account, doctor, that every year new investigations suddenly appear, new procedures because they are based a lot on old techniques, and for a good expert report, we need not the latest technologies, mechanisms have already improved, and I don't know if the mechanisms change. and some aspects of the investigation change, then the structure of the reports should also change. We have to take into account, doctor, that every year new investigations suddenly appear, new procedures because they are based a lot on old techniques, and for a good expert report, we need not the latest technologies, mechanisms have already improved, and I don't know if the mechanisms change. and some aspects of the investigation change, then the structure of the reports should also change.

Well, regarding this last question, although it is true there is a lot to implement but I consider that in order to continue implementing we must first reinforce the areas of criminalistics that are already available, because it is useless you can continue implementing if the quality is going to continue to be deficient, no, besides, like my colleagues, I also consider that staff should be trained more, but also equipment and adequate infrastructure should be acquired, and little by little, this will be able to address more areas such as those that you may have already mentioned, psychology, forensic psychiatry, odorology, and various areas, but not in this way, bone little by little, while the others are already more reinforced and according to that, to be able to decentralize the laboratories to carry out the investigations in provinces or in districts and, in this way to have a better this investigation.

Yes, doctor, and well, the other day I watched a video from the Public Ministry where a report was made on the expert witness Dr. Danny Humpire Molina, who is the expert manager of the Institute of Legal Medicine and Forensic Sciences, Public Ministry, he is a forensic anthropologist and When you were doing your report, you indicated, they asked you no, because you know that carrying out any type of expert opinion in the case of organized crime is usually very dangerous in the sense that the people, the relatives of the accused, usually take measures not , criminal measures, such as threats, because they are the ones who affirm if the person does not, the way of walking, moving and moving, then in this case doctor, when they asked him that, and what would happen if it happens to him something, he said yes something happens to me no, Well,

I'm not afraid of death, but if something happens to me, I don't know what would happen to my cases, so when he said that, he said I don't know if they're going to handle it well or they're going to handle it badly, I don't know what kind of result will be, positive or negative, then we can conclude that sometimes a person, if they have greater capacity, no, because of the experience they have had, as my colleague had mentioned, the systematization of the experience, because he doubted that this case was going to be handled in the best way by another expert, so if he would share all his knowledge, and so on, the experts could give conferences on what is the best way to handle a case, which strategies can be adjusted. So I think that with that extensive experience that they have, they could share it with their colleagues and thus all carry out an expert examination, but in the best way, that results in positive results.

high-tech materials and equipment and some aspects that have been carried out in other countries, together with the updates regarding the training, there was a very important detail, not only should it be with people who are working as experts at the national level but also internationally to be able to make improvements to a high cutting edge. That's all, thank you very much

Interventions and answers of (E4)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?

I have already finished with my question in what you stated, you considered that in Peru we are not so prepared to carry out all the procedures due to lack of investment in personnel, infrastructure and equipment; Although it is true that objective evidence can be obtained and the personnel can be trained, but if there is no equipment and infrastructure to be able to carry out these procedures, the results will not be 100% valid. In addition, the implementation of the laboratories is not found in all the provinces that can require these services, these are centralized in the capital, making it difficult to transfer the samples and extend the processing time and the obtaining of results.

As far as I am aware, there is INACAL, which is in charge of verifying whether the laboratories are qualified to give it an accreditation and for this to be a backup, because obviously, in order to provide a certification or accreditation to a laboratory, they have to carry out minimum evaluations. how the infrastructure is, yes they have biosafety materials, how they carry out the procedures and are in accordance with the protocols, even the least they always value you if you

are neat with your work, but I don't know if INACAL is in charge of evaluate, for example, the laboratories of the National Police or the laboratories that can be found in the Public Ministry; It says in general that INACAL is the institution in charge of evaluating quality and providing certification, but I don't know if it applies to them.

I understand that INACAL is the Certifying Institution at the national level and is the one who should make the minimum evaluations of how the infrastructure is, if they have biosafety materials, the procedures and if the protocols are good; but I don't know if it is in charge of evaluating, for example, the laboratories of the National Police or the Public Ministry.

Question 02: What are the advantages and disadvantages of the double participation, National Police and the Public Ministry, in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports?

Well my answer is very small but here I state what I think and say that more than disadvantages, I consider that this double participation should exist as long as both institutions have the ability to carry out the procedures and issue reports since in this way The results would be reaffirmed and not only that, there may be procedures that only one of these institutions is capable of carrying out and thus the investigation would be complemented, however, each entity must maintain its powers without interfering or hindering the work of the other, that is all.

I am going to cross-examine, they are two institutions that perform the same function that can have a direct impact on the budget and let's say it diversifies this budget into two, which could be for a single institution, in some places this is not allowed, in such a way that these are united and they have become part of another institution, for example the Ministry of Justice, this explains two things; that the Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office cannot be judge and jury, then this proposal would establish a complete reengineering. Where the personnel would be assigned to this institution with an administration of businessmen, where it is managed basically privately, which allows contact with other private and state international laboratories, which generates competitiveness and development. So on that idea. You

You mentioned that in other countries private persons assumed this function, I believe that it should not be in a particular way, because you know that this lends itself to too many things, and I think that these investigations are too delicate to be exposed in that way. way, for individuals as they say, now it is true that the state has to, as they say, divide this budget between both institutions, which means that infrastructure cannot be improved, personnel cannot be well trained, more

equipment cannot be purchased ,Perhaps there should be an organization, an entity that can accommodate the 2 entities, both the National Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office, obviously for criminal investigations, but as I had already mentioned, both parties have different powers, so they should maintain their line, but both aimed at criminal investigation.

Question 03: Do you know if the criminalistic tasks of the prosecutor, official experts, party experts and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

Well, as far as I am aware, all kinds of investigations are always based on protocols No, in order to ensure the quality of the results, however, from what I have been observing in the transparency portals of both the police and the Ministry Public here these protocols are not found, in the transparency portal, they are not found, therefore they should perhaps have a repository where they can place all the protocols they use; at the time of conducting your investigation, at the time of arrival at the crime scene,

Question 4: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of police, criminal and prosecutorial protocols?

So I think that perhaps the police should have planned well in this case how they were going to enter this place how they were going to capture people, however I think they did not take these security measures into account in the case of the place that It was very small, people couldn't get out, they crowded together and they suffocated to death; now with respect to the chain of custody, I consider that a lot of evidence has also been lost due to the number of people, the relatives who attended, the neighbors; So we know that when people start arriving at a crime scene, reporters, it gets very upset and a lot of evidence is lost, the videos helped, yes, it's true, but I also consider that the way the police entered shouldn't have been that, but they have had to take into account what could happen,

Yes, professor, regarding question 4, well, in these instances it was possible to see through the media that they sent us the information in which, in my opinion, they suddenly would not have taken into account the manuals, the guides, the procedures that were already stipulated and that they know; they would not have acted based on it, on the contrary no, there is an issue of lack of coordination, so each one tried to do their own thing or suddenly they would have been annoyed that these people are throwing a party, in an emergency period and Suddenly this motivated them,

no, it prompted them to react in this way, then they did not respect these protocols and as such they did not respect the protocols, the consequences were not seen, the consequences that we have all seen, now regarding the prosecution and chain of custody everything was also altered no, given the circumstance also of the form of intervention from that moment everything was altered no, then it can also be seen that the videos had been altered they had eliminated some images so everything was It changed, the protocols came to nothing, no, and everything was chaos on that day, the day itself and the next day, all the people, the communication media got in the way; well, the area, the scene itself which was going to be studied how these events had occurred and everything was chaos on that day, the day itself and the next day all the people, the media hindered; well, the area, the scene itself which was going to be studied how these events had occurred and everything was chaos on that day, the day itself and the next day all the people, the media hindered; well, the area, the scene itself which was going to be studied how these events had occurred

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

Well, this place, although it is true, did not have the minimum security measures to operate, therefore I believe that it did not have permits and licenses for its operation, Now it is true that the municipality with its serenazgo team of being attentive to any type of situation in these places, it was not the first time that in a state of emergency these parties were held in said place and neighbors had already stated that there were always party noises or perhaps brawls, now apart from that I do not know if You were able to verify but if they advertised these clandestine parties: then it is very strange that the municipal officials did not realize that these parties were being held and I believe that this should be left open for investigations.

Now with respect to the integrated health network systems and DIGESA, I also consider that they have had to carry out the evaluations not only of the people participating in these parties but also of those who lived around them, no, since they were considered to be the red ones to be able to, well, yes there were more infected regarding covid-19, that would be all

This nightclub did not comply with minimum security measures, it did not have auxiliary escape doors, every venue must always have an auxiliary exit door when it comes to large venues, an example, although cinemas sound redundant, they did not have it, it was only a single entrance

and very narrow, so it did not comply with that security measure it did not have escape doors, despite innumerable regulations that regulate throughout our country, for the operation of said premises that bring together a collective number of people, for that reason I consider that, finally, I consider that there is both administrative and functional responsibility on the part of the mayor's officials. By way of conclusions, the administrative authorities within their function in the same sense correspond to them at this time to carry out the corresponding review,

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

then we have a general analysis to close this meeting from your perception what change do you think should be implemented to improve right now for example fossil formation

No, but nevertheless within everything I also have some criminal specialties of forensic sciences that have not yet been developed or are very incipient in our reality, so the question is what do you think should be implemented, should some other forensic sciences be implemented, or only, well, all of a sudden improve what we have

Anything to add?

What my partner shared, I found very interesting about being able to have an institution that can provide you with theoretical-practical knowledge about criminalistics, because although it is true here in Peru to be able to be an expert you have to specialize, however I have seen that, in other countries, there are universities where you go out as a criminalistics and criminology graduate. And that is very interesting because from the beginning they focus on this type of investigation, however, here you have to seek by your own means to be able to specialize, for example, me to be able to enter this master's degree I, if I have been researching and there were only three universities that offered you this type of master's degree, the others did not offer you or were simply focused on other types of careers or something like that, I don't remember well or I was also at the police institute which, as my colleague mentions, is only aimed at those who are police officers, but those of us who are interested in taking up this career, access is quite limited,

so I think I should try to implement and apart from implementing, to make this career more known, which at least for me is very interesting and very important, no, at the moment of clarifying this type of crimes that here in Peru we see what the daily bread is, no, and well I believe that in order for us to have better and more valid research, we should have institutions that can provide this type of knowledge, no, even to be able to do internships it is very limited, for example in the Public Ministry, you cannot do pre-professional internships or professionals, because if it is true that the data they handle is confidential but, and what about those who want to learn about this branch that is very interesting, then access and knowledge should not be so limited, at least not in our country, because in other countries, yes, it is seen that there are degrees in criminalistics or criminology, that would be all.

Interventions and answers of (E5)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?

Well, to begin institutionally, as soon as we are prepared, since criminal activity includes activities and procedures, as has already been mentioned by other comrades of a meticulous nature to demonstrate and correctly and effectively recreate the events that occurred using the instruments, weapons and everything anything to do with the crime scene. Always based on scientific knowledge and techniques, to syndicate the perpetrators of the crime, so the answer would be that we are not prepared at the organizational level, since the institutions responsible for providing Citizen Security and also the administration of justice have not adopted preventive measures. whenever I can say a phrase "We have not learned from the mistakes of the past" unfortunately the institutions have not learned, the criminalistic manuals, operational manuals, the protocols exist, but nevertheless, unfortunately it is as if they were on paper, they are not being applied, there is also a lack of training for the personnel in charge of criminalistic tasks, the logistics necessarily, only when the facts happen We just thought about it. And the ideal would be that we who are in public institutions have a pending task of adjusting these criminal procedures and others that help a better investigation. only when the facts happen do we just reflect on it. And the ideal would be that we who are in public institutions have a pending task of adjusting these criminal procedures and others that help a better investigation. only when the facts happen do we just reflect on it. And the ideal would be that we who are in public institutions have a pending task of adjusting these criminal procedures and others that help a better investigation.

I have not heard of an institution that is in charge of the procedures of I am aware if there is an institution that is in charge of the issue of the quality of criminal proceedings, it is true, in attention to my colleagues who preceded me, yes, well, I have heard that briefly about INACAL but I am not certain that it is committed to this procedure, perhaps the most relevant or important thing would be to implement an agency that would be in charge, in any case if it exists, that will publicize its functions, we from the administration of justice perhaps We could give an account of some progress in the investigations that are carried out in the prosecution, from my point of view in the prosecution we always get some documents, surveys, fill out some forms, but not specifically about criminal proceedings, In one way or another, another institution that approaches but does not see criminal procedures would be the crime observatory that has other functions, but perhaps another body attached to it can be created to see criminal aspects.

Question 2: What are the advantages and disadvantages of the dual participation of the National Police and the Public Ministry in criminal procedures and the issuance of expert reports?

Although it is true that the investigation corresponds to the National Police and the Public Ministry, according to the allocation of the constitution and basically the criminal procedure code of 2004, they say that the person in charge of directing the criminal investigation is the Public Ministry, however I believe that what the MP has to do is basically a legal control of the investigation and the operational work has to be carried out clearly by the National Police, obviously what the public ministry has to do is to control this operational work of the police in subjection to the fundamental rights raised in the constitution so that everything is in accordance, so that there is no type of violation or something in this regard; That is why I believe that, more than a separate function, it is a dual function.

In this question that you mention, it would be interesting perhaps to have a specialized criminalistics unit that is made up of personnel from the national police and public ministry, I would agree in that sense as long as it has the logistical personnel and human resources suitable; Previously, a few years ago, there was a figure from the National Police of Peru. I say for the purpose of illustrating a little that it was called the investigation police, purely investigation. It would be interesting perhaps, although I don't know if we would be prepared to assume this, our reality is necessarily different from that of other countries, but it would be interesting, obviously it would be in charge of the state,

Question 3: Do you know if the criminalistic work of the prosecutor, official experts, party experts and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

Indeed, if there are action protocols even for particular cases such as criminal flagrante delicto of inter-institutional action, if they are posted,

There is even a portal that standardizes all this, the implementation team of the new criminal procedure code, what happens is that these are not very well publicized. Some time ago I was looking for some protocols to realize that it was on a page, there is a page that is Legis.pe that has posted these action protocols in one, two or three publications, it is a page that helps us a lot, I think They are not going to let me lie to those who know the law that it is helping us a lot, in recent years that it has been implemented; but I believe that this work more than a group of investigators, I believe that it is up to the state to publicize it, this work is still pending because these are for investigators, judges, prosecutors, but also for the general public,

Question 4: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of police, criminal and prosecutorial protocols?

Well, it is evidently an indication, as I have learned from the media and from some friends who are participating in the investigation of this crime, because indeed the issue of the chain of custody was not respected as it should be, precisely when the event occurred. of Thomas restobar, people outside the investigation came very close to the premises, perhaps the work of the police was not the most effective either, some protocols were not respected, it seems that it is precisely a little controversial, because basically in northern Lima, the districts Prosecutors in Lima itself are already applying the 2004 Criminal Procedure Code, but it seems that the police entities did not respect much what the chain of custody is, and other procedures that must be followed for this type of case, I think perhaps that there was not good communication between the police and the representative of the Public Prosecutor's Office, because obviously in an event like this the police must report immediately, but I understand that the police did report the event immediately, however the The MP was a little late, being the MP I cannot defend the indefensible, so to speak no, we already talked in the previous questions that the head of the criminal action is the Public Prosecutor's Office, it must also fulfill its obligation, it could be an event that happened in the wee hours of the morning, it cannot be used as an excuse that basically it happened at dawn, when a

prosecutor is on duty he is on duty 24 hours a day, when a prosecutor dispatches he is on duty 24 hours a day hours of the day, In any case, there should have been personnel or prosecutors who had to be attentive to the fact. No, in conclusion, what I want to say is that this issue of the chain of custody was not respected at all, likewise, some were not taken into account. basic criminalistic procedures, as I say and I mention at times, the principles of criminalistics were also not taken into account, perhaps to properly address this type of investigation, there was an incorrect synergy between the police and the representative of the Public Ministry. As I say and I mention at times, the principles of criminalistics were also not taken into account, perhaps to properly address this type of investigation, there was an incorrect synergy between the police and the representative of the Public Ministry. As I say and I mention at times, the principles of criminalistics were also not taken into account, perhaps to properly address this type of investigation, there was an incorrect synergy between the police and the representative of the Public Ministry.

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

responsibility on the part of these institutions, greater control must be exercised. We are always going to relive the case of utopia, if there had been greater control, a tragedy from back then could have been avoided, the same thing happened here, perhaps if the Municipality had had a more active role in controlling what was happening, with that unexpected visit from the serenazgo, but unfortunately this was not done, this is something that to date represents a great tragedy, we are already talking about Utopia, we are already talking about Thomas Restobar, who knows if a similar tragedy will happen in the future, god no want, if we do not exercise preventive control, the municipality can establish sanctions, fines, but what is the use of this if they are not going to be controlling, that these are not executed, for example, when they carry the temporary or definitive closure, which we are talking about.

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

This question summarizes a little what we have already been talking about, definitely on the subject of criminal proceedings, there is a pending task that the State must solve, in order to

resolve some problems that have been presented, I think that before making any changes add or remove or whatever, first you have to do an analysis of everything you've done so far, an analysis, a judgment and put it into a technical report, and through the technical report you can see what is you have done well, what you have done wrong and to the extent of that we would implement. Well, an action plan to elaborate greater strategies that allow to reinforce, then, the improvement of the criminalistic study in our country,

I am thinking that research is limited by unoptimized research capabilities, for various reasons that as I have talked about in question number one, two, lack of technology, lack of accreditation, optimization, etc. You also have to see that there is a high number of cases that are assigned to the investigator, just as it happens in the judiciary or the Public Ministry, which we know as the burden, it is also given to them, there is also a high rotation of investigators, they are transferred to other places, there is also an absence of a standardized format for expert investigation reports, among others. So what is it that I propose? I think there should be an inter-institutional coordination of criminal investigation, which includes the MP, PNP, PJ, other auxiliary bodies, including also the INPE, because you also have to see that there many ask for prison benefits, for example, I am going to concretize in something concrete, I am going to take two crimes: extortion and exaction; then it is necessary to prepare a standard format for the presentation of a report of the results of the criminal investigation, in each of the types of crimes of extortion and exaction, another point could be to formulate protocols or guides as previously discussed of the criminal investigation in each of the types of extortion and extortion crimes, another is to draw up a specific regulation on how to make these protocols or how it should be designed in the criminal investigation for all cases of extortion and exaction, and thus, design what an extortion program is. capacity building that allows a successful implementation of the standard format,

Anything to add?

Undoubtedly, the strengthening of criminalistics is related to several factors, the first factor is the creation of a school of experts, criminalistics is closely attached to law, although it is true that they are sciences that are related, they are very different, they have a very closeness between the science of law and criminal procedures in general, is a pending task that also remains for the different organs of administration of justice to be able to have the improvement of criminal science in general, also due to the increase in the crime rate in the country. , we are aware that there is a

pending task, the justice administration bodies also have to account for it, often saying the justice system is bad, it is bad; but then to form or create technical reports, is going wrong, in that sense,

Interventions and answers of (E6)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?

There are two types of experts in Peru: Experts who are professionals in the fields of medicine, biology, chemistry, dentistry, psychology, engineering and others; who emanate from universities and who initially studied at a university of origin to obtain a degree, and then specialized in one way or another have obtained a second professional degree in a certain forensic field; That is why these experts make up the National Registry of Specialists (RNE), so although it is true that the quality of these experts is distinguished by this condition. However, there is also another type of expert who does not have a professional degree, since their expertise and knowledge goes hand in hand with the development of disciplines, procedures, forensic techniques, that represents them as in other countries of the world and can fully develop, that I think should be so, to be able from a human being point of view or otherwise academic university branches made up of internationally certified experts, which could also be an alternative, so that they can give that important accreditation to an expert who faces a judicial level and simply without that knowledge, sometimes the reports are quite subjective based on his little knowledge that he perceived in his training; Finally, it is necessary to give this accreditation so that the level of quality is high, on the other hand it is also true that the state must support and finance the various technological means such as there are in Europe. Then the accreditation, professionalization,

I have been able to perceive, then, from the response of each one of you, that almost all of us agree that training first, then training, and third, certification, would basically be related to personnel, infrastructure, equipment, and documents, that is, protocols. manuals and guides that despite existing are not used correctly that order of ideas that I just did

There must be an institution in charge of supervising criminalistic work and determining that quality, while in all kinds of private companies or industries, and also some public ones, there is always an area, a sector that is in charge of quality so that a product can go to market.

There is not in Peru a body that in reality on criminal products in different entities, be it the Public Ministry or the National Police, is supervising or ruling at the expert level, the only level of control is when the expert is interrogated or cross-examined, how he has obtained his expertise,

but at the procedural level an administrative control does not exist, but there should be a state body to determine quality, it may be from the professionals who with their expertise can give, but not all have the same training, there are many factors, but it should exist.

Question 2: What are the advantages and disadvantages of dual participation, the National Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office, in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports?

In any case, you can use the MP personnel when you have mistrust on the part of the national police, as is the case of these young people who died and who indicated many theories as to whether they were lead pellets or marbles; the prosecutor in charge determined that this be carried out by MP experts.

Integrate the criminalistics laboratories of the PNP and MP, I am listening to the opinions of colleagues, their proposal could be, because if in civil life the judiciary has the REPEG, and they have different professionals and then when the asset is going to be appraised property, they indicate how much is the cost that the interested party has to pay, as a result of the trial that is later returned to him, and he pays a part of the costs, but it is under the rule of the Law that comes later, then here it is It could have something similar, but a state control body is needed that in this situation can demand quality, it could also provide training, create a school of experts, but the state has to control it, a way to control a private body, but at the same time invest in technology; It's a very interesting idea.

Question 3: Do you know if the criminalistic work of the prosecutor, official experts, party experts and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

I am not going to repeat the same Dr. If there are protocols, there are also guidelines, for example the 2015 guidelines regulate the procedures of the Gesell chamber and also the psychological reports for prison benefits. I agree with colleagues' opinion that there is no publicity for them on institutional transparency portals, which should be at the service of the community, of the general public, only for researchers like most of us, we have to be resorting to pages of researchers to be able to inform us.

Question 4: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of police, criminal and prosecutorial protocols?

what was happening at that time when there were prohibitions and procedures for a state of emergency and also a general health emergency, then this happened, it happened that a group of more than 100 people went up to the second floor, there was a party, there were meetings, they simply notified the police, so they could see what was happening, the police were not prepared, they did not know what was happening at the top, the number of people; and when they intervened there was a stampede of so many people and with the consequent death on the stairs, and what was seen on television; the doors were broken, because even the police themselves were being attacked, so that is what I am giving attention to, that here there has been a surprise, in any case, who would have thought that in a place where traffic was prohibited,

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

Well, I am not going to repeat what my colleagues have already pointed out, the only thing I am going to say is that the Prosecutor's Office has opened proceedings for three crimes: manslaughter, wrongful injury, non-compliance with sanitary measures. I consider that the preventive function according to your fifth question has been carried out according to the function of both the direction of the North Lima integrated health networks and the General Directorate of Environmental Health, which was seen in the videos that all the people were being analyzed with the tests and right after it came out that almost all of them had infections because they had all been together, or all of them were imprisoned with the majority of the people, as far as I think that the responsibility is criminal with respect to the Municipality of Los Olivos, with Regarding the mayor because it stopped carrying out its function, which was to supervise, and I knew that it lacked permits, for so many people, that is, the capacity was 5 times more than the capacity that the premises should have had, therefore I consider that the officials in charge of the municipality of olivos, such as the revenue department, works office, etc., and other competent areas, I imagine that the prosecutor in charge should consider in order to include it in the investigation being carried out by the Public Ministry. Said premises did not have the corresponding permits or licenses for said discotheque, moreover, I think it was closed, because it had been sanctioned previously, so it can be seen that said discotheque did not comply with minimum security measures, it did not have auxiliary escape doors , Every venue should always have an auxiliary exit door when it comes to

large venues, an example, although it sounds redundant, the cinemas, did not have it, it was only a single entrance and very narrow, so it did not comply with that security measure, it did not have doors of escape, in spite of innumerable normative existence that regulates in all our country, for an operation of these premises that brings together a collective number of people, for that reason I consider that, finally, I consider that there is both administrative and functional responsibility, on the part of the civil servants of the mayor. By way of conclusion, the administrative authorities within their function in the same sense correspond to them at this time to carry out the corresponding review, withdrawal of licenses, closures of said premises, because something similar will be repeated at another time,

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

I'm thinking no, that research is limited by unoptimized research capabilities, for various reasons that, as I have discussed in question number one, two, lack of technology, lack of accreditation, optimization, etc. It is also necessary to see what a high number of cases is assigned to the investigator, just as it happens in the judiciary or the Public Ministry, which we know as the burden, it is also given to them, there is also a high rotation of investigators, they are transferred to other places, there is also an absence of a standardized format for expert investigation reports, among others. So what is it that I propose? I think there should be an inter-institutional coordination of criminal investigation, which includes the MP, PNP, PJ, other auxiliary bodies, including also the INPE, because you also have to see that there many ask for prison benefits, for example, I am going to concretize in something concrete, I am going to take two crimes: extortion and exaction; then it is necessary to prepare a standard format for the presentation of a report of the results of the criminal investigation, in each of the types of crimes of extortion and exaction, another point could be to formulate protocols or guides as in the past we talked about the criminal investigation in each of the types of crimes of extortion and exaction, another to draft a specific regulation on how to make these protocols or how it should be designed in the criminal investigation for all cases of extortion and exaction, and not like that,

Interventions and answers of (E7)

Question 1: How are we prepared to guarantee the quality of the results of criminal proceedings?

Of course, as the team from the criminalistics area was currently telling you, based on this situation in the Restobar, what would have happened, possibly it did not have the capacity or the ideal ideas, the ideal criminalistic procedures to guarantee the quality of these results that are would carry out in this investigation.

Yes, well. From that part I also don't know since I haven't had the opportunity to be in this area for my career. I would not be able to specify if there is any institution that supervises its procedures, but in general and realizing the situation, it would be good if there were some institution that could monitor or monitor since human beings learn or in some way require that pressure. to be able to do things right.

Question 2: What are the advantages and disadvantages of dual participation, the National Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office, in criminal proceedings and the issuance of expert reports?

Well, I was saying that with respect to question two, it is not possibly the advantage is that both instances, the National Police and the Public Ministry, work together and that this can benefit the formalization of a tax complaint, that is the advantage, the work in team coordination communication.

In terms of disadvantages, I could talk about one of the institutions not carrying out its work properly, for example, that the National Police of Peru does not provide the expert reports that the user requires, so that they can be evaluated in Legal Medicine, Psychological or others; and this somehow, if these means do not exist, a tax complaint could not be formalized either.

Question 03: Do you know if the criminalistic tasks of the prosecutor, official experts, party experts and investigations have action protocols for their work and if these are found in the portals of institutional transparency?

Well, this aspect is also known to exist in these manuals, protocols, to carry out some skills, in terms of the psychological field, you can have access when you are inside the institution, but in general the way to find them in portals is not You get it in a complete way, maybe the cover and certain pages can be there, but you don't get the whole manual in a complete way.

Question 4: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the institutions involved, in terms of opportunity, application, prosecution and chain of custody, of the police, criminal and prosecutorial protocols?

I agree with my colleagues, they have not been applied correctly despite the fact that these are structured, however, due to lack of planning, inter-institutional organization and adequate training of institutional actors for the management of their respective guides and protocols.

Question 5: What is your opinion about the THOMAS RESTOBAR case and the action of the municipality of Los Olivos, the Directorate of Integrated Health Networks North Lima-DIRIS North Lima and the General Directorate of Environmental Health-DIGESA of the Ministry of Health ?

Yes, professor, well, regarding this to question 5 no, regarding the action of the municipality Well, it can be assumed that they knew because the media would have already reported this situation, so there, I would describe it as a situation in which they are ignoring what that they are reporting, then suddenly if they had intervened in time, they would have identified this situation, perhaps this whole situation would not have occurred, no, on the other hand, the authorities of that district, well, they had to take the corresponding actions since we were in the emergency period and with our curfew time at 10 at night, so what were these people doing at that time, in this place, concentrated, not respecting social distance, and that many of these people who would have been there I would have had this COVID, then a total disregard for the entire population in general that in some way would be complying with their state of emergency and that they would be in their homes, on the other hand there is the issue of the directorate of integrated networks DIRIS Lima Norte, all these entities watch over our health, for the health of all human beings and especially in this District in this situation has been due to suddenly promoting as a plan before and after no, before, suddenly discarding, monitoring the patients who are found to be positive, all of this, to raise awareness among the population, this would be before, later because it happened, all the people who had been there were discarded and, well, nothing else was known, also if it is that they would have been following him or not, or if these people would have kept their quarantine period or not, then this whole situation anyway, instead of our society, our country continuing to cope with this pandemic that we are going through, on the contrary, no, everything was declining more and that also it drags everyone as citizens, not that would be my opinion.

Question 6: From your perception, what changes do you consider should be implemented to improve criminalistic work, for example, training of criminal profilers, dynamic retrospective, forensic planimetry, others?

Well, actually with this last question, if you have seen, implementations, with the aim of improving but suddenly they are complying with us, for example, the pilot program was established so that the assistants take administrative office positions in the police stations, and what they said so that the police can leave and no longer be able to just sit at a machine doing administrative work, which was a function, so this pilot program was also implemented where they entered, civilians to carry out these jobs as a parts table, certified copy and all of this, so to date this continues but we have not seen a change either, in the National Police, that we have already taken over these people, and that the policemen have at least been freed from these activities, so we don't know see, you don't see no, then there would have to be a lot of commitment, on the part of these programs and that they be implemented and that they also totally favor from a general way and that they are not taking advantage of, and as we have already been seeing now in these marches that have taken place and that we are always under this system and that this does not change and we continue to turn around in the same way, then there would have to be a lot of commitment on the part of the people, the authorities, the State to implement new strategies, and that you are in this legal field greater probability of improvement, and for this reason, the users also benefit, there would be a lot of work in that aspect, and as far as possible, hopefully it can be fulfilled, more and more and through specialization, with the technologies that we have now, there would be enough compromise in this aspect, that would be my opinion.

Anything to add?

If in this area, as the other colleagues have mentioned, it is very limited, if it is very limited, it is not easily found like, for example, clinical psychology, you can find various courses and training, not graduates, you can find it in a broad, but generally for the part of forensic psychology it is very limited no, and that is why also many people or the staff is minimal no, and it would also not cover the expectation of what a State or some entity in that area wants to request No, then there is also the issue that there are other people who know and who do not share this knowledge, so we are also falling into selfishness there and therefore we would not be learning what they know, on the other hand I also see in this area what this much, each area well the legal part, the social part, the psychological part, each one acts individually and they were not acting together, also creating difficulties, so it would be advisable that they also need trained personnel, these instances also exist to be able to train us more and also be able to develop ourselves in this area and All in all, well, the best ones are going to be given and more so now that young people have that impetus of

wanting to study, that the new generations are there excelling, then that exists and they would have to give themselves the tools and with it also improve everything the system. These instances also exist to be able to train ourselves more and to be able to develop ourselves in this area and within everything, well, the best ones are going to be given and more so now that young people have that impetus of wanting to study, that the new generations are there excelling, then that exists and the tools would have to be given and with it also improve the whole system. These instances also exist to be able to train ourselves more and to be able to develop ourselves in this area and within everything, well, the best ones are going to be given and more so now that young people have that impetus of wanting to study, that the new generations are there excelling, then that exists and the tools would have to be given and with it also improve the whole system.